

FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF ADHESIVE FILMS AND LAMINATING RESINS IN BONDED JOINTS FOR REPAIR PURPOSES

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SUMMARY

An experimental investigation of the crack growth under fatigue loading on bonded joints manufactured with adhesive films and laminating resins is presented with the objective to assess their quality for repair purposes. A methodology based on the real-time monitoring of the compliance during fatigue loading is presented.

Keywords: Fatigue, Bonded Joints, Adhesives, Crack Growth, Repair, Double Cantilever Beam

INTRODUCTION

Repair operations in composite aircraft structures should guarantee that the resulting parts maintain the structural integrity of the pristine component. This includes the static strength, damage tolerance and fatigue durability. The bonded joint between the structure and the patch is the most critical part of the repair. Therefore, it is necessary to develop reliable procedures to assess the fatigue durability of the adhesives or laminating resins used for this purpose. At present, the only standard test related to interlaminar crack growth in composite materials is focused on obtaining onset curves in mode I (the number of cycles to start damaging the specimen) [1]. Crack propagation rates are considered neither in the standards nor in the design procedures. The reason for this is that mode I fatigue tests exhibit large scatter and are extremely costly (long duration and man-labour intensive).

On the one hand, this communication introduces a methodology to determine the fatigue crack growth behaviour (onset and crack growth rates) of bonded joints, which is based on the real-time monitoring of the specimen compliance.

Once the methodology has been presented and discussed, a comparison of the fatigue behaviour between an adhesive film and a laminating resin is conducted with the objective to assess their fatigue damage tolerance of the respective bonded joints for repair purposes.

EXPERIMENTAL

An adhesive film, A2, and a laminating resin, L2, were used to manufacture bonded joints between carbon fibre reinforced pre-cured adherents, AS4 / 8552 unidirectional (UD) prepreg from Hexcel. The ply sequence for the adherents was $[0_2, \pm 45_2]_s$. The adherent panels were pre-cured in autoclave at 180°C and 7 bar. Then, the bonded joint was performed in a furnace with the assistance of a vacuum bag. The adhesive film studied (A2) is normally processed in the autoclave and there was an interest to assess its mechanical performance in "on field" repair conditions, where the use of autoclave is usually precluded. A teflon insert was placed between the adherents so that an initial pre-crack of 25 mm was obtained.

For laminating resin L2, a thermal cycle of 24 hours at room temperature followed by 1 hour at 60°C and 2.5 hours at 120°C was used. The film adhesive was cured at 120°C for 120 minutes. A reference panel of a bonded joint with a well-known adhesive film (ADR) cured under autoclave conditions was also produced. That panel was used as a reference for C-scan through transmission ultrasonic inspection (using a reflectant plate).

Figure 1. Photograph showing the specimen, the side-clamped mechanical fixtures [3] and the placement of the "clip-on-gage" extensometre.

The dimensions of the manufactured panels were 300 x 350 mm and 8 specimens of 250 x 25 were obtained from each one. Each manufactured panel was inspected by ultrasonic through transmission C-scan using a reflectance plate. The specimen and loading configuration correspond to a Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) specimen. The static characterization of the fracture toughness in mode I of the adhesive joints has been presented in another paper to this conference [2].

Mechanical tests were performed in a 25 kN MTS Bionix hydraulic testing machine equipped with a 2.5 kN load cell. A Clip-On Gage extensometre from Epsilon, model 3541-008M-025M-HT1 with 5 mm gage was used to monitor the displacement between

specimen arms during testing, as it can be observed in Figure 1. The real time calculation of the compliance described in the following sections was performed by means of the Calculated Chanel option of the MTS MultiPurpose TestWare® software that controls the system. This option permits to generate an input data from a mathematical combination of the signals of the load and displacement sensors at the same rate as the sensors data are acquired (4 kHz).

The specimens were loaded through a set of mechanical fixtures developed at the University of Girona and now under AIRBUS patent [3].

Figure 1 shows the experimental setup for mechanical testing. The location of the extensometre was chosen so that the displacement of the specimen arms was measured with no influence of the system compliance or possible plays between joints.

METHODOLOGY

The experimental information of interfacial crack growth in composites concerns two aspects. One is the *onset* curves, which indicate the number of cycles, characterized by the peak cyclic value of the energy release rate, G_{max} , and load ratio $R = P_{min}/P_{max}$, required to initiate damage. The initiation of damage at each onset point is established when an increase of the specimen compliance of 1% or 5% is measured. As a result, a G_{max} - N curve is generated which may serve for design purposes, in an equivalent way as the S - N curves are used in metals (see figure 2, where the value of G_{max} has been normalized by critical value of the energy release rate G_c)).

Figure 2. Onset curves for damage initiation. Each onset point results from the identification of the number of cycles at which the specimen compliance as increased by 1 or 5%.

Another experimental interest on crack propagation under cyclic loading is to determine the dependence of the crack growth rate, defined as da/dN where “ a ” is the crack length and “ N ” the number of cycles, on the cyclic loading conditions. The objective of the experimental investigations is to define the complete dependence of da/dN on the three selected parameters that determine the loading state (for example, $da/dN = f(G_{max}, R,$

G_{II}/G_T the mixed mode)). With this information, and for a particular fatigue loading case, the determination of the lifetime of the component before the crack growth reaches a critical length is straightforward. The definition of the dependence of the crack growth rate da/dN on G_{max} , R and G_{II}/G_T implies a large amount of experimental tests. Therefore, most of the studies concern only a limited part of this function by keeping some of the variables constant.

Delamination fatigue tests are scarcely performed in industry due to their complexity and cost and due to the characteristic high scatter of the results. It is so costly because the measurement of the compliance, C , (to identify damage initiation in onset curves) and the measurement of the crack length, a , (to later build the $a(N)$ curve from which the da/dN dependence will be obtained) require the interruption of the cyclic loading and the intervention of the technician (to measure visually the crack length or to perform an static test to determine the specimen's compliance at that moment). Therefore, it is not an automatable procedure, besides the inherent large duration of the fatigue experiments.

In this work, an alternative approach has been followed. It consists on the real time calculation of the specimen's compliance, without stopping the fatigue test. The specimen's compliance under fatigue loading, referred to as dynamic compliance, is calculated as $C = \Delta d/\Delta P$, where d is the displacement, measured by the extensometre and P is the load. Figure 3 shows a sketch of the calculation.

Figure 3. Calculation of the dynamic compliance during cyclic loading

The calculation is performed by means of the Calculated Channels option of the MTS software and permits to obtain the compliance data at the same rate as the data is acquired from the load and displacement sensors (4 kHz). Thus, it becomes, an entirely automated method.

The real time measurement of the compliance leads to a straightforward measurement of *onset* curves. As the compliance is measured continuously the identification of the cycle

at which it has increased a 1% or 5% is direct. Besides the high sampling rate, the scatter reduces dramatically in comparison with the other methods that require the interruption of the test.

In order to determine *crack growth rate* curves, it is necessary to monitor the crack length, a , as a function of the number of cycles, N . In this work, this is accomplished through a compliance calibration, that is, by establishing the C vs. a dependence. This compliance calibration is performed *a posteriori* of the fatigue test. Once the test is finished and the crack length has reached its maximum extension, the mechanical fixtures are moved along the specimen so different effective crack lengths can be explored (see figure 4). For several crack lengths, the dynamic compliance is measured during a fatigue loading with a displacement amplitude matching that of the test (for very few cycles), and a $C(a^3)$ calibration fitting is performed. Then, the $C(N)$ curve can be easily translated to a $a(N)$ curve from which a $\frac{da}{dN}$ can be calculated. Finally, the maximum energy release rate for each cycle, $G_{max}(N)$, can be calculated using the Modified Compliance Calibration [4] using the slope of the $C(a^3)$ fit and the maximum load P_{max} .

Figure 4. The compliance calibration of the specimen is performed after the fatigue test. The side-clamped mechanical fixtures permit to perform tests at different effective crack lengths.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fatigue tests on DCB bonded joints bonded with the adhesive film A2 and laminating resin L2 were performed at constant displacement amplitude, with load ratio $R = d_{min}/d_{max} = 0.5$. The specimens were previously pre-cracked in order to avoid the possible influence of resin pockets at the crack tip of the teflon insert. The maximum amplitude, d_{max} , for each bonded joint was chosen so that the corresponding G_{max} (maximum applied cyclic strain energy release rate) was about 30% of the static fracture toughness, G_{IC} [2]. Then, d_{min} and d_{max} for A2 were 2.438 mm and 1.219 mm, whereas

for the laminating resin L2, they were 0.851 mm and 0.425 mm. Loading frequency was 5 Hz in order to avoid heating of the specimen. The reached number of cycles for the fatigue test on the adhesive film was 9×10^5 cycles, and 2.5×10^5 cycles for the laminating resin.

Figures 5a and 5b show the evolution of the compliance measured during the test for both bonded joints.

Figure 5. Evolution of the compliance with the number of cycles for a) the bonded joint with adhesive film, and b) with laminating resin. Tests were performed at constant displacement amplitude.

As expected, the compliance grows monotonically with the number of cycles. The growing rate of the compliance decreases because the strain energy release rate in DCB specimens depends inversely on the crack length. That is, as the crack length grows with the number of cycles, the driving force for crack extension decreases. In the case of the L2 specimen, there is an unexpected evolution of the crack during the first 3×10^4 cycles.

Figure 6 shows the compliance calibration performed on both specimens after the fatigue test, according to the methodology described above.

Figure 6. Compliance calibration for specimens A2 (open circles) and L2 (crosses)

Crack growth rates curves, $da/dN(G_{max})$, were calculated from the data shown in figures 5 and 6, and the maximum load, $P_{max}(N)$. Figure 7 illustrates the crack growth rates for both bonded joints. Both curves show common trends: a threshold in G_{max} below which the crack tends to arrest, and a domain of G_{max} where the logarithm of the crack growth rates increase linearly with the maximum applied cyclic strain energy release rate. The threshold value, however, is very different: around 150 J/m² for the specimen A2 and around 34 J/m² for specimen L2. It would be expected to observe a faster increase of the crack growth rates when G_{max} approaches the static fracture toughness, G_{IC} ; however this domain was not explored in this work.

Figure 7. Crack growth rate dependence on the driving force for crack extension, G_{max} . Both specimens, A2, L2 exhibit a common behaviour: a threshold value below which the crack tends to arrest and a linear dependence of the $\log(da/dN)$ on G_{max} .

In analogy with metals, delamination growth rate can be expressed as a power law function:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = A(G_{max})^n$$

Figures 8 and 9 show the fits performed to calculate the exponents for both materials. For the bonded joint with adhesive film, A2, the exponent was 7.1, whereas for the specimen bonded with the laminating resin L2, it was 9.9. In both cases the exponent is higher than those encountered in metals (1-2) and in line with the exponents found in delamination experiments in composite materials (6-10). The difference in the exponent between the specimens tested, A2 and L2, indicates a higher sensitivity to cyclic loading of the specimen bonded with the laminating resin.

Figure 8. Fit of $\log(da/dN)$ vs $\log(G_{max})$ to calculate the exponent, n for specimen A2. In this case, $n = 7.1$

Figure 9. Exponent n for specimen L2 was of 9.9.

CONCLUSIONS

As a conclusion, the present work has presented a fully automated methodology for the characterization of bonded joints under fatigue loading in Mode I, which relies on the real time monitoring of the specimen's compliance and its *a posteriori* calibration. The method provides onset curves $G_{max}(N)$ or crack growth rates $da/dn(G_{max})$ with lower scatter than traditional methods relying on the visual inspection of the crack length or on the interruption of the test to monitor the specimen's compliance.

The usefulness of the method has been demonstrated with the analysis of the fatigue behaviour of bonded joints for repair purposes. Two specimens were tested; one bonded with an adhesive film (A2) and the other with a laminating resin (L2). The crack growth rate dependence over the maximum cyclic strain energy release rate G_{max} , showed a threshold value below which the crack tends to arrest. The threshold value is lower in the L2 specimen (34 J/m^2) than in the A2 specimen (150 J/m^2). The sensitivity exponent, n , is higher for the L2 specimen, evidencing a higher sensitivity to cyclic loading. In view of these results, it can be concluded that the adhesive film tested (A2) is more suitable for repair operations than the laminating resin studied (L2) in terms of fatigue performance.

The investigation on these adhesive films and laminating resins is on course with tests on samples in hot/wet conditions, further fatigue tests and by exploring the fracture toughness of the bond when the patch is co-cured with the bonding agent to a pre-cured adherent.

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